

THE ALKALOIDS OF *RAUWOLFIA BEDDOMEI* HOOK. F. PART I

BY S. BOSE, S. K. TALAPATRA AND (MRS.) A. CHATTERJEE

δ-Yohimbine and sarpagine have been isolated from the roots of *Rauwolfia beddomei* Hook.

In connection with our investigations on *Rauwolfia* species, it appeared of interest to examine *Rauwolfia beddomei* Hook, a plant indigenous to South India. This study seemed especially pertinent because of the report (Pillay, Rao and Rao, *Ind. J. Pharm.*, 1955, 17, 91) that the roots of *R. beddomei* contain several alkaloids as revealed from their paper chromatographic examination.

Through the courtesy of Messrs. Rajaranga & Co., Ltd., Madras, some quantity of authentic *R. beddomei* roots has been obtained and a brief study of the alkaloids present in its root-bark is reported herein.

Alkaloids were drained from the powdered roots by cold percolation with ethyl alcohol. Chromatographic resolution of a benzene solution of this crude base (yield 0.022%) over Merck's alumina furnished an alkaloid, C₂₁H₂₄O₃N₂, m.p. 257° (decomp.) (approx. 27% of the total base). It crystallises from ethyl alcohol in prisms containing a molecule of alcohol as solvent of crystallisation. The alkaloid does not produce any characteristic coloration with ferric chloride and is free from :N.CH₃, hydroxyl and methylenedioxy groups. It possesses a side methyl and methoxyl function. It has $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -62.18^\circ$ (chloroform). Its monoacidic character is indicated by conductometric titration and it readily forms a monohydrochloride, C₂₁H₂₄O₃N₂.HCl, m.p. 290° (decomp.). From infra-red (peak absorption at 5.87 and 6.16 μ) and ultraviolet data (increased absorption at 250 m μ) of this alkaloid, the existence of a β -alkoxy-acrylic ester group (I) (Chatterjee and Talapatra, *Science & Culture*, 1955, 20, 568) has been concluded.

The infra-red spectrum also exhibits bands at 2.85 μ (>NH), 7.25 μ ($-\overset{\overset{|}{\text{C}}}{\text{C}}\text{CH}_3$) and 9.05 μ (ether bridge).

The alkaloid has been shown to be a tetrahydro- β -carboline derivative from evidence of colour reactions (Ross[†], Boca and Lobo, *Anal. farm. bioquim.*, 1932, 3, 51). It was, in fact, proved to be identical with *δ*-yohimbine (Chatterjee and Talapatra, *loc. cit.*) by direct comparison of their m.p., properties, ultraviolet and infra-red spectra (Table I) as also of their paper chromatograms.

TABLE I

	<i>δ</i> -Yohimbine from <i>R. beddomel</i> .	<i>δ</i> -Yohimbine from <i>R. serpentina</i> .
Melting point	257-58° (decomp.)	257° (decomp.).
Mol. formula	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂
Optical rotation	[α] _D ²⁵ = - 62.18° (CHCl ₃)	[α] _D ²⁰ = 60° (± 2°) (CHCl ₃)
Solubility	Sparingly soluble in ethanol and methanol; highly soluble in chloroform and pyridine.	Sparingly soluble in ethanol and methanol.
Crystalline form	Prismatic needles from ethanol with one molecule of solvent of crystallisation.	Prisms from ethanol.
U.V. spectrum in ethanol	Maxima at 225, 281 and 292 mμ and increased absorption at 250 mμ.	Maxima at 225 and 283 mμ with strong absorption at 250 mμ.
I.R. spectrum (characteristic bands at)	2.85, 5.87, 6.16 and 9.05 μ	3.1, 5.88, 6.20 and 9.0 μ.
Mol. formula and m.p. of hydrochloride	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ . HCl, 290° (decomp.)	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ . HCl, 280-90° (decomp.)

* Hofmann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 849.

Another base, C₁₀H₂₂O₂N₂, m.p. 364-66° (decomp.), was obtained from the basic resin (vide Experimental) in very poor yield (0.0007%) by employing chromatography technique. It is readily soluble in alkali and reduces Fehling's and ammoniacal silver solutions. It is free from methylenedioxy, N.CH₃, methoxy and carbonyl (ketonic, aldehydic or lactonic) functions. The alkaloid exhibits the following colour reactions which are characteristics of a tetrahydro-β-carboline derivative (Table II).

TABLE II

Reagent.	Colour.	Remarks.
FeCl ₃	Red with pink tinge.	Deepens on keeping.
1% Ceric sulphate in 2N-H ₂ SO ₄	Violet.	Persists for a long time.
Fröhde's reagent	Immediate navy-blue.	Changes to green.
Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ + K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	Navy-blue.	Fades to yellow.
Glyoxal sodium bisulphite + conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Blue with violet tinge.	Gradually acquires greenish tinge.
FeCl ₃ + glacial acetic acid + conc. H ₂ SO ₄ (Keller's reaction)	Light violet.	Persists.

From its properties, melting point and colour reactions (Table III), this alkaloid is shown to be identical with sarpagine, $C_{19}H_{22}O_2N_2$, which has been found to occur in various *Rauwolfia** species, viz., *R. canescens* L. (Keck, *Naturwiss.*, 1955, **42**, 391; Bhattacharji, Dhar and Dhar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 310), *R. serpentina* Benth. (Stoll and Hofmann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 1143; Thomas, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 488; Rodendorf and Lder, *Naturwiss.*, 1953, **40**, 342; *Ber.*, 1954, **87**, 818), *R. heterophylla* Roem ex Schult (Hochstein, Murai, Boegemann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 351), *R. indecora* R.E. Woodson (Ishidate, Okada and Saito, *Bull. Soc. Phar., Japan*, 1955, **3**, 319) and *R. hirsuta* Jacq. (Vergara, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1864). Further work on sarpagine is in progress.

TABLE III

	Sarpagine from <i>R. beddomei</i> .	Sarpagine from <i>R. serpentina</i> . *
Melting point	Sinters and turns brown above 320°; melts at 364-65° with decomposition.	Sinters and turns brown above 320°; melts at 363-64° with decomposition.
Molecular formula	$C_{19}H_{22}O_2N_2$	$C_{19}H_{22}O_2N_2$
Solubility	Moderately soluble in boiling ethanol, less soluble in boiling methanol and least so in acetone; insoluble in chloroform, ether and petroleum ether.	Soluble in 60 parts boiling ethanol, 250 parts methanol, and about 400 parts acetone; insoluble in chloroform, ether and petroleum ether.
Crystalline form	Fine needles with one molecule of ethanol of crystallisation.	Fine needles with one molecule of ethanol of crystallisation.
NaOH solution	Dissolves.	Dissolves.
Tollen's reagent	Reduced.	Reduced.
Fehling's solution	Do	Do.
Keller's reagent	Violet colour.	Violet colour.
$FeCl_3$ solution	Red with pink tinge.	Pink.

* Stoll and Hofmann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 1143.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dried powdered roots (8.0 kg.) of *Rauwolfia beddomei* were extracted with 95% alcohol (18 litres) containing 0.1% acetic acid in a percolator for a week. The reddish brown alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure on a water-bath to about 200 c.c. The thick deep brown extract was poured into cold water (1.5 litres) containing 1% acetic acid in a thin stream, kept overnight in a refrigerator, and filtered from the separated non-basic resinous mass through a celite bed. The resin was washed several times with 1% acetic acid. The combined filtrates were cooled, extracted with ether (300 c.c. each in 3 instalments) to remove ether-soluble impurities. The aqueous solution was then cooled, covered with 400 c.c. ether and treated with ammonia to pH 8-8.5, when an ether-insoluble basic gum (A) separated. This was removed.

The ethereal portion was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted several times with ether (2 litres in all in 4 instalments). The combined ether extract (showing violet fluorescence) was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and concentrated when a gummy residue was obtained which failed to crystallise from organic solvents or their mixtures. It was dissolved in acetone (about 60 c.c.) and the resulting deep brown solution was chromatographed through a column of alumina (38 cm. $\times$ 2.5 cm.). The chromatogram was eluted with benzene and other solvents. Eluates were collected in fractions of 30 c.c. (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Chromatography of the crude ether-soluble base of R. beddomei.

Eluents.	Fractions.	Residue on evaporation.
Benzene	1	0.56 g. Crystallises from alcohol, m.p. 252-53° (dec.)
Do	2-5	0.6 g. Do
Do	6-7	Nil
Benzene + 50% acetone	8-9	0.3 g. Gummy, uncrystallisable
Do	10	Nil
Acetone	11-12	0.2 g. Uncrystallisable
Do	13	Nil
Alcohol	14	Nil
Chloroform	15-16	0.05 g. Uncrystallisable.

Fractions (1-5) crystallised from alcohol in prisms (yield 0.55 g.), m.p. 252-54° (decomp.). The purification of the base (for analytical purpose) was done by several recrystallisations from methanol and from ethanol, when shining prismatic needles, m.p. 257-58° (decomp.), were obtained. It is sparingly soluble in methanol, ethanol and benzene, fairly in acetone, readily in pyridine and chloroform and insoluble in light petroleum ether and water. The alkaloid (0.42 g.), crystallised from ethanol, lost 0.0487 g. in weight when dried at 140° for 16 hours in vacuo over P_2O_5 and the shining transparent crystals turned opaque. The crystals had the approximate composition: $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_2$, C_2H_5OH .

0.402 g. of the substance in 10 c.c. chloroform showed a rotation of -2.5° in 1 d.cm. tube at 25°, whence $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -62.18^\circ$. [Found in a dry sample: C, 71.87; H, 7.05; N, 8.00; OMe, 0.82; :C.Me, 4.01; M. W., 356.3 (potentiometric titration; 0.1005 g. of the base consumed 2.82 c.c. of 0.1 N-HCl). Calc. for $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_2$: C, 71.59; H, 6.81; N, 7.95; OMe, 8.80; :C.Me, 4.26 per cent. M.W., 352].

The alkaloid did not show any depression in m.p. when admixed with an authentic sample of δ -yohimbine.

Hydrochloride of the Base (δ -Yohimbine).—The base (0.1 g.) was dissolved in hot aqueous HCl (2N, 5 c.c.) and the solution upon cooling produced δ -yohimbine hydrochloride (0.095 g.). It crystallised from water in fine leaflets, m.p. 290° (decomp.). [Found in a dry specimen: C, 64.64; H, 6.43; N, 7.23; Cl, 9.46. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_2$, HCl: C, 64.85; H, 6.43; N, 7.20; Cl, 9.13 per cent].

Isolation of Sarpagine from R. beddomei Hook.—The basic gum (A) (*vide supra*) was dried, mixed with an equal amount of sand and soxhletted for 16 hours with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated to about 50 c.c., cooled and chromatographed through a column of alumina (45 cm. $\times$ 2.5 cm.) using benzene and other solvents as eluents. Eluates were collected in fractions (30 c.c. each) (Table V).

TABLE V

Eluents.	Fraction.	Residue on evaporation.
Benzene	1: Dark reddish brown solution with green fluorescence.	Gummy.
Do	2: Same.	Gummy.
Do	3: Reddish yellow solution with strong green fluorescence.	Needle-shaped crystals m.p. 362° (decomp.).
Do	4	Little residue, few crystals, m.p. 362° (decomp.).
Do	5	Nil
Benzene + 50% acetone	6-7	Trace of uncrystallisable residue
Acetone	8-9	Same
Chloroform	10	Same.

Fractions 3 and 4, when triturated with methanol, deposited fine silky needles, m.p. 362° (decomp.), (0.06 g.). These were filtered and washed from the adhering gum with ice-cold acetone. Sarpagine, thus obtained, was purified by several crystallisations from ethanol when colorless needles with alcohol of crystallisation, melting at 364-65° (sintering and turning brown above 320°) with decomposition, separated out. The base (38.9 mg.) lost ethanol of crystallisation (5.1 mg.) and turned opaque after complete drying in vacuo over P_2O_5 at 140° for 20 hours. (Found in a dry sample: C, 73.64; H, 7.42; N, 9.19. $C_{11}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73.52; H, 7.15; N, 9.03 per cent). The base did not show any depression in m.p. when admixed with an authentic sample of sarpagine.

Potentiometric Titration of Sarpagine.—An alcoholic solution of dry sarpagine (19.5 mg.) consumed 0.64 c.c. of 0.1N-HCl when titrated potentiometrically, whence mol. wt. = 304.7. $C_{11}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires M W., 310.

Hydrochloride of Sarpagine.—For the isolation of sarpagine hydrochloride, the solution left after potentiometric titration (*vide supra*) was worked up according to the method of Stoll and Hofmann (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 38, 1143). The hydrochloride crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles which decomposed above 225°. [Found in a dry specimen: C, 65.64; H, 6.52; N, 8.15; Cl, 9.93. $C_{11}H_{22}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires C, 65.80; H, 6.63; N, 8.08; Cl, 10.24 per cent].

Fractions 1, 2, 6, 9 (Table V) and fractions 8, 9, 11, 12, 15 and 6 (Table IV) responded to Dragendorff's test for alkaloids, indicating thereby that some other basic components were concealed in these fractions which could not be obtained in crystalline state as yet.

In conclusion the authors wish to acknowledge their grateful thanks to Dr W. Schoniger, Sandoz A. G. Basel, Switzerland, for microanalyses, Dr. A. Stoll, Sandoz A. G., Basel, Switzerland for the generous gift of an authentic sample of sarpagine, to Dr. J. M. Mueller, Ciba Pharma Ltd., Switzerland for I. R. spectrum of δ -yohimbine and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (India) for financial assistance to one of them (S.K.T.).

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
CALCUTTA-9.

Received April 26, 1955